

Curing Ultra Large Incomplete Data by Parallel Fractional Hot Deck Imputation

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Abstract—For reliable machine learning and statistical inference with large/big data, curing incomplete data is critical. Fractional hot deck imputation (FHDI) cures multivariate missing data by filling each missing unit with multiple observed values (thus, hot-deck) without resorting to distributional assumptions. By inheriting the power of FHDI and parallel computing, we developed ultra data-oriented parallel FHDI (named as UP-FHDI) to cure ultra incomplete data with tremendous instances (big- n) and high dimensionality (big- p). We enabled scalable ultra incomplete data curing and also devised variance estimation via a parallel Jackknife method as well as efficient ultra data-oriented parallel linearization techniques. Results confirm that UP-FHDI can cure ultra datasets, up to millions instances and 10,000 variables. We validate the accuracy and scalability of UP-FHDI, paving a new pathway for reliable machine learning and statistical inference with “cured” big data.

Index Terms—Ultra data-oriented parallel fractional hot-deck imputation, big incomplete data, high dimensional missing data curing, parallel linearized variance estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Inadequate handling of missing data may lead to biased or incorrect statistical inference and subsequent machine learning [1]. Naive imputation may lead to inconsistent bias with the presence of considerable inequality in the missingness across different variables. Amongst many imputation methods, the multiple imputation proposed by Rubin [2] was one of the most popular methods. However, it requires the so-called “congeniality” and “self-efficiency” conditions [3], thereby restricting practical applicability in broad science and engineering. We found generality and broad applicability from fractional hot-deck imputation (FHDI) which is a non-parametric imputation method and creates a complete data with fractional weights after imputation while preserving joint probability of the observed data. Some of the authors of this paper developed the R package “FHDI” [4] to cure general multivariate incomplete datasets without prior distributional assumptions. Although we enter into a new era of big data, large incomplete data-oriented imputation software is still beyond the reach of global researchers. Some of the authors of this paper developed an initial version of parallel FHDI (named as P-FHDI) by leveraging high-performance computing (HPC)

technologies [5], yet it has several limits. This paper briefly summarizes how we expanded and sophisticated the initial P-FHDI to give rise to the ultra data-oriented UP-FHDI so that we can tackle ultra incomplete data with easy (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Three types of datasets: (a) $n \gg K^p$; (b) $n \leq K^p$; (c) n and p are both very large, where K is the number of categories of imputation cells.

II. KEY PROCEDURES OF UP-FHDI

A. Basic Setup

Suppose a finite population \mathcal{U} with p -dimensional continuous variables $\mathbf{y} = \{\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_p\}$, and y_{il} represents the i th instance of the l th variable where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ and $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$. Given the number of categories K , one can discretize continuous variables \mathbf{y} to discrete variables \mathbf{z} , so-called “imputation cells,” such that \mathbf{z} take values within categories $\{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ for each variable. One can decompose an instance $\mathbf{y}_i = \{\mathbf{y}_{i,obs}, \mathbf{y}_{i,mis}\}$ as the observed and missing part, respectively. Similarly, we can decompose $\mathbf{z}_i = \{\mathbf{z}_{i,obs}, \mathbf{z}_{i,mis}\}$. Let \mathcal{A} be the index set with size of n selected by a probability sampling mechanism. Consider \mathcal{A}_M as the index set of missing units such that $\mathcal{A}_M = \{i \in \mathcal{A}; \prod_{l=1}^p \delta_{il} = 0\}$; alternatively index set with observed units is $\mathcal{A}_R = \{i \in \mathcal{A}; \prod_{l=1}^p \delta_{il} = 1\}$ such that $\mathcal{A}_M \cup \mathcal{A}_R = \mathcal{A}$. A response indicator function δ_{il} takes the value of 1 if y_{il} is observed, otherwise $\delta_{il} = 0$. Imputation cells \mathbf{z} consists of missing patterns $\mathbf{z}_M = \{\mathbf{z}_i \mid i \in \mathcal{A}_M\}$ and observed patterns $\mathbf{z}_R = \{\mathbf{z}_i \mid i \in \mathcal{A}_R\}$. The cross classification of all variables form imputations cells \mathbf{z} and we assume a cell mean model:

$$\mathbf{y} \mid (\mathbf{z}_1 = K_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_p = K_p) \sim (\boldsymbol{\mu}_{K_1, \dots, K_p}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{K_1, \dots, K_p}) \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{K_1, \dots, K_p}$ is a vector of cell means and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{K_1, \dots, K_p}$ is the variance-covariance matrix of \mathbf{y} in cell $(K_1 \dots K_p)$. Then utilizing a finite mixture model under missing at random (MAR) condition, the conditional distribution of $f(\mathbf{y}_{i, mis} | \mathbf{y}_{i, obs})$ is approximated by

$$f(\mathbf{y}_{i, mis} | \mathbf{y}_{i, obs}) \cong \sum_{g=1}^K p(\mathbf{z}_i = g | \mathbf{y}_{i, obs}) f(\mathbf{y}_{i, mis} | \mathbf{y}_{i, obs}, \mathbf{z}_i = g), \quad (2)$$

where $p(\mathbf{z}_i = g | \mathbf{y}_{i, obs})$ is the conditional cell probability and $f(\mathbf{y}_{i, mis} | \mathbf{y}_{i, obs}, \mathbf{z}_i = g)$ is the within-cell conditional density of $\mathbf{y}_{i, mis}$ given $\mathbf{y}_{i, obs}$ derived from (1).

B. Imputation Cell Construction and Variable Reduction

Considering \mathbf{z}_M and \mathbf{z}_R , we can obtain index set of unique missing patterns $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_M = \{i, j \in \mathbf{A}_M | \forall i \neq j, \mathbf{z}_i \neq \mathbf{z}_j\}$ of size \tilde{n}_M and unique observed patterns $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_R = \{i, j \in \mathbf{A}_R | \forall i \neq j, \mathbf{z}_i \neq \mathbf{z}_j\}$ with size of \tilde{n}_R , respectively. Sequentially, we can further extract the unique missing patterns $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_M = \{\mathbf{z}_i | i \in \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_M\}$ and unique observed patterns $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_R = \{\mathbf{z}_i | i \in \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_R\}$. Let $\mathbf{D}_i \in \mathbb{N}^{M_i}$ be the indices of donors of the i th recipient $\mathbf{z}_i = \{\mathbf{z}_{i, obs}, \mathbf{z}_{i, mis}\}$ where $\mathbf{D}_i = \{j \in \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_R | \mathbf{z}_{i, obs} = \mathbf{z}_{j, obs}\}$ with size of M_i . Note that M_i is the number of donors of the i th recipient. We can perform exhausted search over $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_R$ to obtain index set of donors of all recipients $\mathbf{L} = \{\mathbf{D}_i | i \in \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_M\}$. Meanwhile, we derive a set of the number of total donors of all recipients $\mathbf{M} = \{M_i | i \in \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_M\}$. The initial \mathbf{z} may not guarantee at least two donors for each recipient to capture the variability from imputation. Denote the minimum entity of \mathbf{M} be m . If $m \geq 2$, the cell construction will terminate. Otherwise, we will apply the KNN method to determine deficient donors. Let $e \in \mathbb{R}^{\tilde{n}_R}$ be the Euclidean distance (ED) between a recipient \mathbf{z}_i and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_R$. Let \mathbf{w} be the index set of observed units in \mathbf{z}_i . If \mathbf{z}_i has less than two donors such that $M_i < 2$, the k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm consists of the following steps:

- (1) Compute e by $e = \frac{\tilde{n}_R}{j=1} \sqrt{\sum_{l \in \mathbf{w}} \left(\frac{z_{il}}{k_l} - \frac{\tilde{z}_{R(j,l)}}{k_l} \right)^2}$ where $\tilde{z}_{R(j,l)} \in \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_R$; k_l is total categories of \mathbf{z}_l .
- (2) Suppose e_{t_1} is the minimum entity of e . Add t_1 to \mathbf{D}_i and update M_i . If $M_i \geq 2$, stop.
- (3) Suppose e_{t_2} is the second minimum entity of e . Add t_2 to \mathbf{D}_i and update M_i .

We will apply KNN method until $m \geq 2$.

UP-FHDI overcomes the curse of dimensionality by adopting the sure independence screening (SIS) of [6] for ultra-high dimensional variable reduction. Suppose we select v variables for a recipient such that $v \ll p$. Let $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_q\}$ be always observed and $\mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_w\}$ be subject to missingness such that $p = q + w$. Consider $\mathbf{r}_k = (r_k^1, r_k^2, \dots, r_k^q)$ as a vector of sample correlations of \mathbf{X} given \mathbf{Y}_k . The adopted SIS algorithm consists of the following steps:

- (1) Compute correlation vectors \mathbf{r}_k where $k \in \{1, \dots, w\}$ and sort them in descending order.
- (2) Define sub-covariate set M_k for imputing \mathbf{Y}_k , $k \in \{1, \dots, w\}$ such that $M_k = \{1 \leq i \leq q; r_k^i \text{ is among top of the largest } v, \text{ where } r_k^i \in \mathbf{r}_k\}$.

- (3) We are implicitly assuming that $P(\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_w | \mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_q) = P(\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_w | \mathbf{X}^*)$ where \mathbf{X}^* is the covariates such that $M = \cap_{k=1}^w M_k$ or $M = \cup_{k=1}^w M_k$.
- (4) If the number of selected covariates in M equals v , then stop. Otherwise, repeat step (2) and (3) by setting $v = v + 1$ until we obtain v selected variables.

C. Modified Expectation Maximization (EM) Scheme

We extend EM scheme for UP-FHDI with the selected (reduced) variables. Let \mathbf{X}_k^* be the set of important covariates selected for \mathbf{Y}_k by SIS. Let $\mathbf{X}^* = \cup_{j=k}^w \mathbf{X}_k^*$ or $\mathbf{X}^* = \cap_{j=k}^w \mathbf{X}_k^*$ or be covariates derived by a global ranking of sample correlations. We assume that $\mathbf{X}^* \subset \mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_q\}$. Consider $\mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_w\}$ as a w -dimensional categorical random vector with support \mathcal{C} . The $\pi_c(\mathbf{x}^*) = P(\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{c} | \mathbf{x}^*)$ be the conditional probability of $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{c}$ given $\mathbf{X}^* = \mathbf{x}^*$. Note that $\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \pi_c(\mathbf{x}^*) = 1$. E-step computes conditional probability

$$p_i^{(t)}(\mathbf{c}) \equiv P^{(t)}(\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{c} | \mathbf{x}_i^*, \mathbf{y}_{i, obs}) = I(\mathbf{y}_{i, obs} = \mathbf{c}_{obs(i)}) \cdot P^{(t)}(\mathbf{y}_{i, mis} = \mathbf{c}_{mis(i)} | \mathbf{x}_i^*, \mathbf{y}_{i, obs}), \quad (3)$$

where $\{\mathbf{c}_{obs(i)}, \mathbf{c}_{mis(i)}\}$ is a partition of \mathbf{c} based on the missing pattern in unit i . And $P^{(t)}(\mathbf{y}_{i, mis} = \mathbf{c}_{mis(i)} | \mathbf{x}_i^*, \mathbf{y}_{i, obs})$ is

$$P^{(t)} = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi_c^{(t)}(\mathbf{x}_i^*)}{\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}_i} \pi_c^{(t)}(\mathbf{x}_i^*)} & \text{if } \mathbf{y}_{i, obs} = \mathbf{c}_{obs(i)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

and $\mathcal{C}_i = \{\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{C}; \mathbf{y}_{i, obs} = \mathbf{c}_{obs(i)}\}$ is the subset of \mathcal{C} whose $\mathbf{c}_{obs(i)}$ components are equal to $\mathbf{y}_{i, obs}$. M-step updates the conditional probability as

$$\pi_c^{(t+1)}(\mathbf{x}^*) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n I(\mathbf{x}_i^* = \mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}_{i, obs} = \mathbf{c}_{obs(i)}) p_i^{(t)}(\mathbf{c})}{\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{i=1}^n I(\mathbf{x}_i^* = \mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}_{i, obs} = \mathbf{c}_{obs(i)}) p_i^{(t)}(\mathbf{c})}. \quad (5)$$

D. Parallel Imputation

Using the joint cell probability obtained the modified EM scheme of the previous section and using the imputation cell constructed, we can proceed imputation of missing cells in accordance with FHDI (see details in [4]). For parallel imputation task, this paper adopts the most of the parallel computing version (see full descriptions of parallel imputations in [5]).

E. Fast and Efficient Variance Estimation

The Jackknife variance estimation had been successfully implemented into P-FHDI [5]. However, it is not applicable for ultra data owing to the computational bottlenecks. To overcome this challenge, we developed a parallel linearized variance estimation technique based on one of the author's prior work [7]. Consider variance estimation of a deterministic imputation. Assume the original sample is decomposed into G disjoint groups. The sample observations follow the cell mean model: $y_i | i \in A_g \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} (\mu_g, \sigma_g^2)$ where A_g is the index set of group g . Let n_g and r_g be the number of elements and the number of observed elements in group g , respectively. Assume the response mechanism is MAR and the parameter of interest is $\theta = E(Y)$. We will use a deterministic imputation with

$\hat{\eta} = (\hat{\mu}_1, \dots, \hat{\mu}_G)$, where $\hat{\mu}_g = r_g^{-1} \sum_{i \in A_g} \delta_i y_i$ is the g th cell mean of y among respondents. The imputed estimator of θ will be

$$\hat{\theta}_I = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{g=1}^G \sum_{i \in A_g} \{\delta_i y_i + (1 - \delta_i) \hat{\mu}_g\} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{g=1}^G n_g \hat{\mu}_g. \quad (6)$$

Writing $e_{ig} = y_i - \mu_g$ for $i \in A_g$, we can express

$$\hat{\theta}_I = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{g=1}^G \left\{ n_g \mu_g + \frac{n_g}{r_g} \sum_{i \in A_g} \delta_i e_{ig} \right\}.$$

Using $E(e_{ig}) = 0$, the uncertainty associated with n_g/r_g is asymptotically negligible. Thus, the imputed estimator $\hat{\theta}_I$ can be expressed by $\hat{\theta}_I \cong \frac{1}{n} \sum_{g=1}^G \sum_{i \in A_g} \left\{ \mu_g + \frac{1}{p_g} \delta_i (y_i - \mu_g) \right\}$ where p_g is the probability limit of r_g/n_g . The resulting variance estimator is $\hat{V}(\hat{\theta}_I) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{g=1}^G \sum_{i \in A_g} (\hat{d}_{gi} - \bar{d}_n)^2$, where $\hat{d}_{gi} = \hat{\mu}_g + \frac{n_g}{r_g} \delta_i (y_i - \hat{\mu}_g)$, and $\bar{d}_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{g=1}^G \sum_{i \in A_g} \hat{d}_{gi}$. We can extend the linearization formula for the variance of the mean estimator of FHDI with multivariate missing data, where M imputed values are randomly selected from respondents in the same imputation cell. The FHDI estimator of the mean of \mathbf{y}_l is given by $\hat{\mu}_{l, FHDI} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \{\delta_{il} y_{il} + (1 - \delta_{il}) \bar{y}_{il}^*\}$, where $\bar{y}_{il}^* = M^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^M y_{il}^{*(j)}$. Assume each unit i in the sample belong to one and only one imputation cell. Let \bar{y}_{gl} be the sample mean of \mathbf{y}_l among the respondents in cell g such that $\bar{y}_{gl} = \frac{1}{r_{gl}} \sum_{i \in S_{gl}} \delta_{il} y_{il}$, where $S_{gl} \in \mathbb{N}^{n_{gl}}$ is the index set of the units in imputation cell g . And r_{gl} is the number of observed units (i.e., $\delta_i = 1$) in cell g of \mathbf{y}_l . The variance estimator of $\hat{\mu}_{l, FHDI}$ can be expressed by

$$\hat{V}(\hat{\mu}_{l, FHDI}) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{\eta}_{il} - \bar{\eta}_l)^2, \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\eta}_{il} = \delta_{il} \bar{y}_{gl} + (1 - \delta_{il}) \bar{y}_{il}^* + \delta_{il} \frac{n_{gl}}{r_{gl}} (y_{il} - \bar{y}_{gl})$, and $\bar{\eta}_l = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\eta}_{il}$. The standard error of $\hat{\mu}_{l, FHDI}$ is computed by $SE(\hat{\mu}_{l, FHDI}) = \sqrt{\hat{V}(\hat{\mu}_{l, FHDI})}$.

III. SPECIAL PARALLELISM FOR UP-FHDI

Fig. 2. Parallel file system on multiple writers and readers. The IO communication between slave processors and the hard drive is conveyed by `MPI_File_Read` and `MPI_File_Write` routines. The OOOPS optimally throttles the IO workload (solid green circles).

Fig. 2 visualizes the parallel file system adopted for UP-FHDI. This system targets the HPC environment that allows simultaneous access from multiple compute servers. The parallel file system supports IO communication between slave processors and the hard drive by cooperative parallel IO in MPI. We adopt IO routines `MPI_File_Read` (denoted as `MPI_RD`) and `MPI_File_Write` (denoted as `MPI_WR`) to read or write from multiple processes to a single binary file on the hard drive simultaneously. The MPI parallel IO is superior to non-parallel IO because its operations are collective such that IO is scalable. Recently, [8] developed the Optimal Overload IO Protection System (OOOPS) to automatically detect and throttle the IO workload. We apply this tool with UP-FHDI to allow administrators to dynamically adjust IO during the job without interruption. This parallel file system resolves efficient memory usage and out-of-memory problems.

IV. VALIDATION AND SCALABILITY TEST

To validate UP-FHDI's accuracy, we conduct Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. Let B be how many MC simulations run; Key steps consist of: **(MC1)** Generate synthetic data by $Y_1 = 1 + e_1, Y_2 = 2 + \rho e_1 + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} e_2, Y_3 = Y_1 + e_3, Y_4 = -1 + 0.5 Y_3 + e_4$, where e_1, e_2, e_4 are randomly generated by the standard normal distribution such that standard deviation (SD) is 1. The term e_3 is randomly generated by the gamma distribution. Thus, $\mu_1 = 1, \mu_2 = 2, \mu_3 = 2$, and $\mu_4 = 0$. **(MC2)** Create 30% missingness to the synthetic data. **(MC3)** Perform imputation of UP-FHDI with random donor selection. **(MC4)** Perform Jackknife variance estimation. **(MC5)** Repeat steps (MC1) to (MC4) over B times. The relative bias (RB) of the standard error of the imputed point estimator (i.e., mean estimator) \tilde{Y}_{FHDI} is defined as $RB = \frac{E(\widehat{SE}) - SE(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI})}{SE(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI})}$ where \widehat{SE} is the square root of the variance estimator $\hat{V}(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI})$ and $SE(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI})$ is the square root of the sampling variance of the mean estimator \tilde{Y}_{FHDI} . And $E(\widehat{SE}) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \sqrt{\hat{V}(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI}^{(b)})}$ where $\hat{V}(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI}^{(b)})$ is the variance estimator from the b th MC sample. $SE(\tilde{Y}_{FHDI}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B (\tilde{Y}_{FHDI}^{(b)} - \bar{Y}_{FHDI})^2}$ where $\tilde{Y}_{FHDI}^{(b)}$ is the imputed point estimator from the b th MC sample and \bar{Y}_{FHDI} is $\bar{Y}_{FHDI} = \frac{\sum_{b=1}^B \tilde{Y}_{FHDI}^{(b)}}{B}$. We present the results of MC simulations of UP-FHDI using SIS with four selected variables (Table I). Dataset is denoted by $\mathbf{U}(n, p, \text{missing rate})$. The mean estimates \bar{Y}_{FHDI} from MC simulations have negligible differences with true column mean μ , confirming the accuracy of UP-FHDI. The average RB over 24 variables in Table I is 2.87%. Overall, the Jackknife variance estimator performs in a favorable manner. We investigate whether the linearized variance estimator is an accurate substitute for the Jackknife variance estimator, and found that the performance of Jackknife and linearization gradually converges to an acceptable datum as datasets become large. We confirm an alignment between linearized and the Jackknife variance estimators with a minor ADSE in Table II with an ultra dataset.

Here, absolute difference of standard errors (ADSE) is defined as $ADSE := \frac{1}{p} \sum_{l=1}^p AD_l = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{l=1}^p \frac{\widehat{SE}_{Linear,l} - \widehat{SE}_{Jack,l}}{\widehat{SE}_{Jack,l}}$ where AD_l is the absolute difference between $\widehat{SE}_{Linear,l}$ and $\widehat{SE}_{Jack,l}$. Note that $\widehat{SE}_{Linear,l}$ and $\widehat{SE}_{Jack,l}$ are the standard errors of mean estimator of \mathbf{y}_l using linearization techniques and Jackknife method, respectively. The linearized variance estimator is a good alternative for the Jackknife variance estimator for ultra data (e.g., $n \geq 20,000$). We compare the performance of naive imputation and UP-FHDI with multiple ultra datasets, randomly generated with a user-defined SD. The naive estimator is a simple mean estimator computed using observed values. As expected, UP-FHDI outperforms the naive method in terms of average \widehat{SE} and $RMSE$ in Table III. Average \widehat{SE} is $1/p \sum_{l=1}^p \widehat{SE}_l$. Also, we conducted scalability

TABLE I

MC RESULTS OF UP-FHDI WITH THE JACKKNIFE METHOD BASED ON 2000 SIMULATIONS. $U(1000, 24, 0.3)$; 4 SELECTED VARIABLES.

	\mathbf{y}_1	\mathbf{y}_2	\mathbf{y}_3	...	\mathbf{y}_{24}
$E(\widehat{SE})$	0.0367	0.0386	0.0525	...	0.0547
$SE(\widehat{Y}_{FHDI})$	0.0354	0.0372	0.0511	...	0.0534
RB (%)	3.82	3.81	2.68	...	2.50
\widehat{Y}_{FHDI}	1.001	2.000	2.001	...	-0.002
true μ	1	2	2	...	0

TABLE II

ADSE BETWEEN JACKKNIFE AND LINEARIZED VARIANCE ESTIMATORS. INPUT $U(10,000, 0.1M, 0.3)$; 4 SELECTED VARIABLES BY SIS

Methods	\mathbf{y}_1	\mathbf{y}_2	\mathbf{y}_3	\mathbf{y}_4	...	ADSE
\widehat{SE}_{Jack}	0.0096	0.0164	0.0189	0.0178	...	
\widehat{SE}_{Linear}	0.0097	0.0166	0.0193	0.0181	...	
AD	0.99%	1.17%	1.79%	1.73%	...	1.41%

TABLE III

COMPARISON BETWEEN UP-FHDI AND NAIVE IMPUTATION WITH $U(10000, 0.1M, 0.3)$; 4 SELECTED VARIABLES USING SIS

SD	(a) Average \widehat{SE}		SD	(b) RMSE	
	UP-FHDI	Naive		UP-FHDI	Naive
3	0.052	0.062	3	0.078	0.084
5	0.084	0.100	5	0.081	0.091
8	0.134	0.160	8	0.083	0.096

tests of UP-FHDI with two ultra datasets in Fig. 3. UP-FHDI yields favorable scaling performance and agrees with the cost models of speedup and running time. Due to the inevitable use of non-contiguous IO, UP-FHDI does not exhibit the ideal linear speedup, which shall be a future extension.

V. CONCLUSION

In a new era of big data and powerful computing, there is a strong need for a big data-oriented imputation tool for reliable data-driven scientific discovery. By inheriting power of the general-purpose, assumption-free data-curing tool FHDI, this paper proposed the ultra data-oriented parallel FHDI (UP-FHDI). We briefly introduce the new aspects of UP-FHDI. The

Fig. 3. Speedup of UP-FHDI with input datasets $U(10000, 0.1M, 0.3)$ and $U(0.1M, 10000, 0.3)$. Note that we adopt 4 selected variables for SIS.

Monte Carlo simulations affirm the validity of UP-FHDI, and the scalability tests confirm scalability. This research outcome will help big incomplete data curing and ultimately facilitate the subsequent machine learning and statistical inference with the “cured” big data. Details of the algorithms, theories, parallel computing techniques, examples, and impact study on the subsequent deep learning will be made available on the authors’ dedicated full paper [9]. UP-FHDI’s program, data, and examples will be available upon request to the authors.

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